

Quantification of air pollution exposure to in-pram babies and mitigation strategies

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ARTICLE INFO

Handling Editor: Xavier Querol

Keywords:

Baby pram
Double pram
Pram covers
Ultrafine particles
Particulate matter exposure

ABSTRACT

Young children are particularly vulnerable to air pollution exposure during their early childhood development, yet research on exposure to in-pram babies in different types of single/double prams is limited. This work aims to mimic their exposure to multiple air pollutants – particulate matter $\leq 10 \mu\text{m}$ in aerodynamic diameter (PM_{10}), $\leq 2.5 \mu\text{m}$ ($\text{PM}_{2.5}$; fine particles), $\leq 1 \mu\text{m}$ (PM_1), $\leq 0.10 \mu\text{m}$ (measured as particle number concentration, PNC) – in three different types of prams (single pram facing the road; single pram facing parents; double pram facing the road). We also assessed the differences in exposure concentrations between typical adult and in-pram baby breathing height via simultaneous measurements besides assessing their physico-chemical properties (morphology and elemental composition). In addition, we analysed the impact of pram covers in mitigating in-pram exposure concentrations of selected pollutants. We carried out a total of 89 single runs, repeating on a 2.1 km long pre-defined route between an origin-destination pair (the University of Surrey to a local school) during the morning (08:00–10:00 h; local time) and afternoon (15:00–17:00 h) hours. These runs simulated morning drop-off and afternoon pick-off times of school children. Overall, the experimental runs took about 66 h and covered the total length of 145 km. Substantial variability is observed in measured concentrations of different pollutants within each run (e.g., up to 290-times for PNC) and between different runs performed during different times of the day (e.g., $\sim 62\%$ variability in average PNC; $\sim 7\%$ for PM_1 and 8% for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ during morning versus afternoon). The average in-pram concentration of fine particles was always higher by up to 44% compared with adult breathing height during both morning and afternoon runs. The comparison of exposure concentrations at two different sitting heights of double pram showed that PNC concentrations were higher by about 72% at the bottom seat compared to the top seat. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) analysis of $\text{PM}_{2.5-10}$ revealed traces of brake wear, tyre wear and re-suspended dust minerals with the predominance of brake and tyre wear emissions at baby height compared with a relatively larger share of earth crust elements at adult height. For mitigation measures, pram covers reduced concentrations of small-sized particles by as much as 39% (fine particles) and 43% (coarse particles). Our results reinforce the need for mitigating exposures to in-pram babies, especially at urban pollution hotspots such as busy congested roads, bus stops, and traffic intersections.

1. Introduction

Air pollution is a topmost environmental health risk, accounting for almost 6.4 million deaths per year (Forouzanfar et al., 2016; Landrigan et al., 2018, 2019; Smith et al., 2014). Young children are among the most sensitive and vulnerable groups due to their higher breathing rates

compared to that of adults (Supplementary Information, SI, Table S1) because children breathing rate per unit of body weight is almost double that of adult (Ginsberg et al., 2005). Moreover, young children have rapidly growing and developing organ systems and traffic-related air pollutants (TRAP) can affect their neurodevelopment (Alemany et al., 2018; Perera, 2017), respiratory systems (Bowatte et al., 2015;

Abbreviations: EDS, energy-dispersive X-ray spectrometry; $\text{DP}_{\text{FR-C}}$, double pram facing roadside with cover; $\text{DP}_{\text{FR-WC}}$, double pram facing roadside without cover; NO_x , nitrogen oxides; PNC, particle number concentration; PM_x , particulate matter less than or equal to $x \mu\text{m}$ in aerodynamic diameter; PTFE, polytetrafluoroethylene; SEM, scanning electron microscope; $\text{SP}_{\text{FP-C}}$, single pram facing parent with cover; $\text{SP}_{\text{FP-WC}}$, single pram facing parent without cover; $\text{SP}_{\text{FR-C}}$, single pram facing roadside with cover; $\text{SP}_{\text{FR-WC}}$, single pram facing roadside without cover; TI, traffic intersection; TRAP, traffic-related air pollutants; TSP, total suspended particles; UFP, ultrafine particles

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.105671>

Received 4 December 2019; Received in revised form 9 February 2020; Accepted 16 March 2020

Available online 08 April 2020

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Bråbäck and Forsberg, 2009; Iskandar et al., 2011; Kanchongkittiphon et al., 2015; Khreis et al., 2017; McConnell et al., 2002; Perera, 2017), cognitive development (Forns et al., 2015; Freire et al., 2010; Lertxundi et al., 2019; Sears et al., 2020; Suglia et al., 2007; Sunyer Deu et al., 2017; Sunyer et al., 2015) and lower functional integration; segregation in key brain networks including slower brain maturation (Pujol et al., 2016) and cause higher blood sugar levels (Zhang et al., 2019). Many recent studies (Boothe and Baldauf, 2020; Bose et al., 2019; Lavigne et al., 2019; Lertxundi et al., 2019; Rivas et al., 2019; Vrijheid et al., 2016) are based on negative health impacts of the prenatal and perinatal exposure to TRAP. Prenatal and perinatal TRAP exposure is found to be linked with following health effects – (i) $PM_{2.5}$: loss in fundamental cognitive abilities, including working memory and conflict attentional network (Lavigne et al., 2019; Rivas et al., 2019) and alteration in sleeping programming (Bose et al., 2019); (ii) UFPs: childhood asthma (Lavigne et al., 2019); (iii) PM_{10} : childhood obesity, hypertension deterioration of asthma, and poor lung function development (Vrijheid et al., 2016).

Here, we refer the term young children to babies, toddlers or infants that are less than three years old (CDC, 2017; Farlexinc., 2003; MediLexicon, 2018). These comprise 6.3% of the total population of the Guildford during the 2011 census year (ONS, 2011). We also use the expressions pram, buggy and stroller interchangeably. The focus of our current study relies on particulate matter in diameter $\leq 10 \mu m$ (PM_{10}), between $2.5 \mu m$ and $10 \mu m$ ($PM_{2.5-10}$; coarse particles), $\leq 2.5 \mu m$ ($PM_{2.5}$; fine particles), $\leq 1 \mu m$ (PM_1), $\leq 0.10 \mu m$ (UFPs; defined as ultrafine particles) for assessing the exposure to adults and in-pram babies. UFPs are measured by their number (Kumar et al., 2010). Hence we have used the words particle number concentration (PNC) and UFP interchangeably. These pollutants show the greatest impact on human health and were therefore chosen for measurements (Heal et al., 2012; Iskandar et al., 2011; Sunyer et al., 2015; Kumar et al., 2018).

Our earlier work (Sharma and Kumar, 2018) discussed the negative health effects of TRAP on young children and highlighted the research gaps and potential mitigation strategies. This work highlighted that the UFPs are highly toxic on per unit mass basis due to their larger surface area and advance pulmonary deposition efficiency (Branco et al., 2014; Donaldson et al., 2005; Harrison and Yin, 2000; Kumar et al., 2010; Sioutas et al., 2005). These are capable of critically damaging respiratory systems, cause alterations in inflammatory biomarkers, penetrate bodies or circulation systems and can accumulate in brains or lymph nodes (Heal et al., 2012; Kumar et al., 2014; Lavigne et al., 2019; Oliveira et al., 2019). Young children breathe higher air pollutant doses in proportion to their lung size and body weight when compared to adults (Rivas et al., 2018). They are highly vulnerable to air pollutant exposure given that they have developing tissues, lungs, immune system, brain and permeable cell membrane lining inside their respiratory systems (Bates, 1995; Buonanno et al., 2013; Burtcher and Schüpp, 2012; Mendell and Heath, 2005; Sharma and Kumar, 2018; World Health Organization, 2005). Young children from deprived sections of the society are distinctively susceptible to such risks in contrast with their equivalents from reasonably prosperous social and financial standing (Mehta et al., 2014; Perera, 2017). Statistically significant linkages were reported between the concentrations of pollutants such as $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} with the occurrences of asthma and allergic rhinitis among young children (Chen et al., 2019; Garcia et al., 2019; Heal et al., 2012; Iskandar et al., 2011; Téllez-Rojo et al., 2020). For instance, Khreis et al. (2017) conducted a meta-analysis of 41 observational epidemiological studies. They examined the linkages between TRAP exposures and the consequent development of asthma in children from birth to 18 years of age. They found the overall random-effects risk estimates (95% CI) as 1.03 (1.01, 1.05) per $1 \mu g m^{-3}$ increase of $PM_{2.5}$, and 1.05 (1.02, 1.08) per $2 \mu g m^{-3}$ increase of PM_{10} over the WHO prescribed annual mean concentration limits. Similarly, Luong et al. (2019) performed a meta-analysis to evaluate the relationship between air pollution and risk of wheeze-associated disorders in

children in Southeast Asia. They reported wheeze associated diseases/disorders to be one of the leading causes of emergency department visits and hospitalisations for children worldwide. They found each an increase of each $10 \mu g m^{-3}$ over annual average concentrations of $PM_{2.5}$ or PM_1 was associated with a 1–2% increase in the risk of wheeze-associated disorders. Yolton et al. (2019) reported that exposure to elemental carbon (EC: a component of $PM_{2.5}$) at birth was associated with increased child-reported depression and anxiety, e.g., each $0.25 \mu g m^{-3}$ increase in EC resulted in increase in overall anxiety scores by 2.3 (95% CI, 0.8–3.9; the Spence Children's Anxiety Scale) to 3.5-point (95% CI, 1.6–5.5; Child Depression Inventory 2 scale). These scales assess the symptoms of depression and anxiety. For example, Children's Depression Inventory-2 assesses symptoms of depression within the past two weeks and yields a total depression score. The Spence Children's Anxiety Scale assesses six domains of anxiety including panic/agoraphobia, social phobia, separation anxiety, obsessive compulsive disorder, physical injury fears, and generalized anxiety, as well as a total anxiety score (Yolton et al., 2019).

Table 1 presents a summary of relevant studies that show limited work assessing air pollution exposure to in-pram babies. These studies provide meaningful insight on elevated exposures to in-pram babies by quantifying and comparing exposures at two different breathing heights.

Kumar et al. (2017) quantified the variability in size-resolved particle mass concentrations in the range of $0.25\text{--}32 \mu m$ and PNC in the range of $0.2\text{--}1 \mu m$ for in-pram babies versus adults. They performed mobile measurements over 64 repeated runs for a total distance of 87 km in the Guildford town centre area during morning and afternoon hours. Their study revealed that in-pram babies are exposed to higher $PM_{2.5}$ by 47%, PM_1 by 31% and PNC by 31% during the afternoon pick-up hours of children from school compared with morning drop-off hours. While this work discussed the variability in the morning versus afternoon concentration exposure of in-pram babies, it did not quantify the differential exposure of in-pram babies compared to adults. Likewise, Kenagy et al. (2016) performed stationary measurements along roadside environments in the city of Edinburgh (UK) to assess the differences in NO_2 concentration exposure of in-pram babies (0.8 m above ground level) compared to adults for their respective breathing height (1.25 m). They showed that measured concentrations at lower heights were generally higher by 5–15% relative to greater heights. In a similar study, Galea et al. (2014) performed mobile measurements in Edinburgh city centre at three pre-defined routes for $PM_{2.5}$ exposure at two different heights (0.74 m and 1.36 m). They found contrasting results showing that $PM_{2.5}$ exposures at in-pram baby breathing height were lower by up to 17–51% compared with adult breathing height. Kumar et al. (2017) discussed variability of their results with Galea et al. (2014) since the latter reported reverse trend of higher exposure at adult height compared to in-pram height except for one of the days when both reported same trend (i.e., higher exposure at pram height compared to adult height. These could be due to the shorter monitoring period (6 days) in Galea et al. (2014). Garcia-Algar et al. (2015) performed simultaneous measurements of UFPs in Barcelona at two different heights: 0.55 m for an infant in a stroller and 1.70 m for an adult. They found that in-pram exposure to UFPs and $PM_{2.5}$ in the roadside environment was up to 10% higher than that for an adult while the corresponding values for NO_2 exposure were 5–15% higher for babies (Garcia-Algar et al., 2015). These findings were in line with those reported by Buzzard et al. (2009) emphasising that children breathing around tailpipe height are likely to be exposed to elevated concentrations of UFPs than those breathing at adults heights during walking or standing.

Most of the previous works have used one type of pram and measured limited pollutants. This clearly highlights a gap: how does exposure to multi-pollutants vary in different types of (single/double) prams? We address this question via extensive field measurements for particles in different size ranges (PM_1 , $PM_{2.5}$, PM_{10} , and PNC). The

Table 1
Review of previous studies on air pollution exposure of in-pram babies.

Pollutants	City (country)	Sampling Technique	Measurement heights	Distance in km (time in minutes)	Number of runs (Number of Datasets)	Study Reference
PM _{2.5} PM ₁ PNC	Guildford (U.K)	Mobile Measurements	0.7 m, 1.7 m	87 (1158.7 ± 73.6)	64 (-)	Kumar et al. (2017)
NO ₂	Edinburgh (U.K)	Stationary Monitoring	0.8 m, 2 m	Not Applicable (-)	- (142 pairs of NO ₂ concentrations for adult and baby breathing heights)	Kenagy et al. (2016)
BC	Barcelona (Spain)	Personal and Fixed Site Measurement ¹		Not Applicable (152,640)	Personal measurements for 45 school children	Rivas et al. (2016)
PM _{2.5}	Edinburgh (UK)	Mobile Measurements	0.74 m, 1.36 m	- (6480)	(-) 18 sets of 1-hour run	Galea et al. (2014)
UFP (20–1000 nm)	Barcelona (Spain)	Mobile Measurements	0.55 m, 1.7 m	15 (1200)	15 (52,008 pairs of UFP concentrations)	Garcia-Algar et al. (2015)
PM _{2.5} PM _{2.5} Components (BC, OC, EC) UFP NO ₂	Barcelona (Spain)	Fixed Site Monitoring		Not Applicable (46, 717, 440)	(-) 9–17-hour daily monitoring in 39 schools for 176 days (553 samples)	Rivas et al. (2014)
BC UFP (10–300 nm)	Casino (Italy)	Personal Exposure Monitoring		Not Applicable (-)	24-hour personal measurements for 103 children	Buonanno et al. (2013)
PM (mass and particle number counts; 1–1000 nm) CO CO ₂ NO _x	Morgantown (WV, USA)	Fixed Site Monitoring	0.85 m, 1.65 m	Not Applicable (-)	264 runs each of duration 5.1 and 12.67 seconds	Buzzard et al. (2009)
PM _{2.5} PM ₁₀ PM ₁ PNC UFPs	Guildford (U.K)	Mobile Measurement	0.5 m, 0.7 m, 0.75 m, 0.8 m, 1.7 m	145 km	66	This study

¹Recorded personal exposure assessment of children through time activity diary and measurements; ²Data obtained through modelling.

specific objectives of this study are to (i) quantify the variability in in-pram baby exposure versus adult exposure to TRAP in different types of pram; (ii) understanding the differences in exposure concentrations to in-pram babies at different sitting heights in double pram; (iii) quantifying the impact of pram covers in mitigating in-pram TRAP concentration exposures; (iv) experimentally analysing the physico-chemical properties of particles inhaled by in-pram babies; and (v) highlighting the underlying factors bringing diversity to in-pram exposure.

2. Methodology

2.1. Route characteristics

A pre-defined route between an origin (University of Surrey) and destination (Sandfield Primary School) in a typical town of Guildford (UK) was chosen for mimicking the exposure of parents and in-pram babies (Fig. 1). The route is selected to represent the daily commuting of parents dropping-off (morning) and picking-up (afternoon) their children to schools. The route passed through three signalised traffic intersections (TIs), two bus stands, a central train station and near a shopping complex to provide diversity in spatial variability across the route in exposure (Fig. 1). A part of the route surrounding the University of Surrey has a low traffic density since none of the main streets passes through the campus. However, local buses frequently cross the campus which may lead to erratic increments of air pollutant

concentrations. The rest of the route goes through a high congested traffic zone. After leaving the University, the route goes on a parallel road to the train railways, passes in front of the Guildford main train station, through the bus station and across some residential area, to reach to the destination (Sandfield Primary School) that is located on a busy road (Fig. 1). For understanding the temporal concentration variations (Section 3.3), the route is divided into 5 segments (Fig. 5): (i) UC (University campus), (ii) BS_{AX} (on-campus bus stop AX in front of AX building), (iii) TC (town centre), (iv) TI₁ (traffic intersection 1 in front of church) and; (v) TI₂ (Traffic intersection 2 in front of Waitrose near the destination i.e., Sandfield Primary School). There was a 15 min stop for stationary measurements at the University of Surrey's campus bus stop 1 (BS_{AX} refers to Bus stop AX) while there was no stopover at the University of Surrey's second bus stop BS_{HS} en route (bus stop on route in front of health science building within university campus). Further details on route characteristics including traffic volume and vehicle kilometres travelled on the sampling route are available in SI Tables S2 and S3, respectively. The route segments TI₁, TI₂ and TC are the most congested segments since these include major roads A322 and A246 with relatively higher traffic volume count compared to that for minor roads in UC segment of the route (SI Table S2).

2.2. Experimental design

Six different scenarios were considered in this study for in-pram field measurements (Table 2). The scenarios vary based on following

Fig. 1. Map of the study route for field measurements. The route length is 2.1 km with origin as the University of Surrey and destination as Sandfield Primary School.

criteria – (i) type of pram used for measurements based on baby seating capacity (e.g., single versus double pram); (ii) measurement heights (e.g., pram height versus adult height; double pram top seat versus bottom seat) and; (iii) use of pram cover (e.g., single pram facing road with cover versus single pram facing without cover) (SI Table S4). These scenarios were covered by a total of 69 single runs (35 in the morning and 34 in the evening) covering a total distance of 145 km over 66 h (i.e., 3947 min). This study included much higher number of total runs compared to past studies, as summarised in Table 1. The repeated runs provided us the repeatability of the data, statistically significant sample size, representativeness of the air quality of the predefined sampling route; and capturing the spatio-temporal

variability. For instance, Peters et al. (2013) investigated the minimum duration of mobile measurements needed to capture the spatiotemporal variation in urban air pollution and to map urban air quality. They demonstrated that a limited number of 20–24 runs carried out on different days and different times of the day over a period of two to three weeks allows to distinguish streets with higher and lower median concentrations of PM₁₀ and UFP in a significant way. According to the classical sampling theory, the sample size (n) needed to compute sample mean with 95% confidence interval is estimated by the following equation, $n = (1.96 \cdot \sigma / e)^2$; where σ is the standard deviation and e is the acceptable margin of error (Kumar, 2009). The first four scenarios include measurements in single prams (42 single runs), with

Table 2
Details of field experiments with different scenarios for data collection on selected route.

Scenario	Measurement types	In-pram Breathing Height (Sitting height)	Measurement time	# of single runs completed	Time (mins)	Distance Covered (kms)
SP _{FP-WC}	Single Pram (facing parent-without cover)	0.7 (0.7 m) ^a	AM	6	375.34	12.6
SP _{FP-C}	Single Pram (facing parent-with cover)	0.7 (0.7 m) ^a	AM	4	262.63	8.4
SP _{FR-WC}	Single Pram (facing roadside – without cover)	0.8 (0.7 m) ^b	AM	6	352.48	12.6 16.8
SP _{FR-C}	Single Pram (facing roadside – with cover)	0.8 (0.7 m) ^b	AM	4	191.68	8.4
DP _{FR-WC}	Double Pram (facing roadside-without cover)	Bottom seat: 0.5 m (0.3 cm)	AM	8	428.64	16.8
		Top seat: 0.75 m (0.5 m)	PM	6	341.37	12.6
DP _{FR-C}	Double Pram (facing roadside– with cover)	Bottom seat: 0.5 m (0.3 cm)	AM	5	286.43	10.5
		Top seat: 0.75 m (0.5 m)	PM	8	422.06	16.8
Total				69 single runs	3947 mins (66 h)	145 km

*Note: AM = Morning; PM = afternoon; Measurement period: 29 days (6 August 2018 to 4th December 2018) for 5 days per week; First set of instruments which is fitted into the pram includes GRIMM (11-C GRIMM Technologies Inc.), P-Trak 8525 (TSI Inc.), Q-Trak and Microaeth (Model MA 200, Aethlabs, USA). Second set of instruments which is fitted into the backpack for adult height measurements include GRIMM (EDM107 GRIMM Technologies Inc.), P-Trak 8525 (TSI Inc.), Q-Trak and Microaeth (Model AE 51, Aethlabs, USA).

^aThe sitting height and breathing height for single pram facing parent (scenario SP_{FP-WC}) are same as this type of pram is used for babies whose age is less than 6 months and babies in such prams sit in resting position with their face facing parent; ^bThe sitting height of single pram facing roadside in scenario SP_{FR-WC} is 0.7 m, which includes a 0.3 m thick foam base which is used for isolation purposes to avoid vibration of instruments of measurements which are fitted on the pram seat. It should be noted that the manufacturer’s seating height for this pram is 0.4 m without use of any foam.

and without pram cover. The last two scenarios include measurements in double pram facing roadside (27 single runs). The field campaign was completed between August and November 2018 (Table 2). Two runs are performed each day; one each during the morning (08:00–10:00 h; local time) and afternoon (15:00–17:00 h). The field campaigns were performed during working days when the school was open. The measurements were performed at four different heights: (i) typical in-pram breathing height (i.e., 0.7 m); (ii) breathing height of adult pushing the pram (1.7 m); (iii) double pram top seat (0.7 m); and (iv) double pram bottom seat (0.5 m). The first four scenarios compare exposures at pram versus adult height while last two scenarios compare exposures at top versus bottom seat (Table 2). The details of filters collected for SEM analysis are presented in Section 2.4.

2.3. Instrumentation and data collection

The measurements were carried out using: (i) optical aerosol spectrometer (EDM 107 and 11-C, GRIMM Technologies Inc., USA) for measuring particles in the 0.25–32 μm diameter range; and (ii) P-Trak (Model 8525, TSI Inc., USA) for measuring PNC in the size range from 0.02 to 0.1 μm . Both instruments measured with a sampling frequency of 6 s. The sensitivity of GRIMM model 11-C is 0.1 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and instrument reproducibility of size-resolved PMC is > 97% over the total measuring (GRIMM ATAGC, 2019). The particle detection range for P-Trak is 0.02 to 1 μm and operating range as 0 to $5 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (Hussein et al., 2017; Thomas et al., 2019). Both aerosol spectrometers were of same make and use the same measurement techniques, yet modest differences could be expected owing to the underlining particle count-to-mass conversion algorithms. For assessing the exposure of in-pram babies and adults, we use two sets of similar instruments, which are fitted into pram and backpack of the adult pushing the pram. The location of the moving pram was acquired every second with a Global Positioning System (GPS) Garmin Oregon 550 (Garmin Ltd., USA). Subsequently, all the data were averaged to 1 min to match the averaging period of all instruments. The meteorological data such as wind direction, wind speed, ambient temperature and relative humidity (SI Table S4) during monitoring periods were obtained from the closest weather monitoring station, situated in Farnborough which is approximately 10 km northwest of Guildford (MetOfficeUK, 2019). Previous studies have utilised data from this meteorological station (Abhijith and Kumar, 2019; Goel and Kumar, 2016).

The data analysis was performed using Excel, Origin and R programming software. The statistical significance of variabilities was tested using t-tests (Welch Two Sample t-test at 5% significance level, $\alpha = 0.05$) for assessing the statistical significance of the variabilities in the measured concentrations of the pollutants during different times of the day such as morning and afternoon hours and for comparing in-pram height versus adult height and double pram bottom versus top sitting height. We found p-values ranged from 2.2×10^{-16} to 0.42. The differences in pollutant concentration (PNC, $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, and $\text{PM}_{2.5-10}$) exposures for in-pram versus adult height were statistically significant with p-values less than 0.001.

2.4. Physico-chemical characterisation

The physico-chemical characterisation of the collected bulk PM particles on Grimm PTFE filters (> 0.12 μm ; filter pore size) is performed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) and energy-dispersive X-ray spectrometry (EDS). For SEM analysis, a total of seven polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) filter samples were collected. These included four samples from mobile measurements (samples 1, 2, 5 and 6; SI Table S5), two samples (samples 3 and 4) from stationary measurements (SI Table S6; co-location exercise; Section 2.5) and one blank filter for quality control purposes. Filter samples 1, and 5 were collected at the in-pram breathing height of 0.7 m while filter samples 2, 3, 4 at adult breathing height (1.7 m) and sample 6 at double pram bottom

seat height (i.e., 0.5 m; SI Table S5). Two of the four samples from mobile measurements were discarded, owing to insufficient mass available on those filters for SEM-EDS analysis. The remaining two filters include one at each of the baby and adult breathing heights. The filters from stationary roadside measurements were used to assess the physico-chemical properties of commonly found elements in a typical roadside environment. The filters had a 47 mm diameter and a nominal thickness of 1000 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. The filter samples were mounted inside two GRIMM instruments (SI Table S5). The filter samples were weighed before and after the exposure using a six-figure (precision to 1 mg) Mettler MT5 top pan microbalance (Mettler-Toledo Ltd., Greifensee, Switzerland). The microanalysis is carried out at the Micro Structural Studies Unit of the University of Surrey (UK) using SEM-EDS analysis. The morphology and the elemental composition are assessed respectively using JEOL SEM (JSM-7100F) and Thermo Scientific™ UltraDry EDS Detector in combination with Pathfinder software by Thermo Fisher Scientific. Further information on EDS analysis is available in SI Section S2.

2.5. Quality control

For quality control purposes, we performed 6 days of co-location field exercise for approximately 27 h, including peak morning and afternoon hours. Two sets of portable high-end instruments for the monitoring of PM (GRIMM EDM107 and 11-C) and PNC (P-TRAK 8525) were co-located side-by-side for intercomparison on the heavily trafficked roadside near the Stoke Park in Guildford (SI Table S7). Such a correction factor based approach is commonly adopted to enhance the equivalence between similar instruments (Zimmerman et al., 2014) and has been adopted in previous studies (Abhijith and Kumar, 2019; Lin et al., 2016). The correction factors were developed using Eqs. (1)–(3).

$$C_{oG,nG} = \frac{PM_{\text{Measurement}} (\mu\text{g m}^{-3})}{PM_{\text{Filter}} (\mu\text{g m}^{-3})} \quad (1)$$

$$PM_{\text{Filter}} (\mu\text{g m}^{-3}) = \frac{\text{Mass collected on grimm filter } (\mu\text{g})}{\text{FlowRate} \left(\frac{\text{L}}{\text{min}} \right) * \left(\frac{\text{m}^3}{1000\text{L}} \right) * \text{time} (\text{min})} \quad (2)$$

$$TSP (\mu\text{g m}^{-3}) = \sum_{k=0}^n \text{Mass of } PM_k \quad (3)$$

$$C_{oG/nG} = \frac{C_{oG}}{C_{nG}} \quad (4)$$

where $C_{oG,nG}$ is a common equation for estimating the correction factor for GRIMM model EDM107 (C_{oG}) or GRIMM model 11-C (C_{nG}). It is defined as the ratio of average PM concentration from GRIMM measurements (i.e., sum of the mass of total suspended particles, TSP, including all PM size fraction in the range of 0.25–34 μm) and mass collected on PTFE filter (i.e., based on total weight on the filter).

$PM_{\text{Measurement}}$ is the sum of the mass of total suspended particles (TSP); PM_{Filter} is the mass collected on the PTFE filter (i.e., based on total weight on filter); TSP refers to total suspended particles including PM in the size range of 0.25–34 μm . $C_{oG/nG} = \frac{C_{oG}}{C_{nG}}$ is the final correction factor to be applied, defined as the ratio of the correction factor for GRIMM model EDM107 to the correction factor for GRIMM model 11-C. Klepeis et al. (2007) reported an error of 10–20% as an indication of good consistency among air pollution instruments including GRIMM. The correction factor between the two instruments was found to be 0.74, which was deemed to be acceptable and no correction factor was applied to the datasets.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Adult versus in-pram exposure

To assess the variabilities in measured concentrations of pollutants

Fig. 2. Box plots of field measurements in-pram and backpack (morning versus afternoon) for (a) PM_1 ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$); (b) $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, (c) $\text{PM}_{2.5-10}$ ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$); (d) PM_{10} (run average; $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$); and PNC (run average; $\#\text{cm}^{-3}$).

(PM and PNC) during morning versus afternoon time of the day, we computed average exposure concentrations (averaged all runs scenario-wise measured at 6 s time interval) for in-pram versus adult height during morning and afternoon hours (SI Table S8; corresponding box plots are presented in SI Figures S1-S2). Here we discuss two scenarios ($\text{SP}_{\text{FP-WC}}$ and $\text{SP}_{\text{FR-WC}}$) to understand the differences in exposure concentrations between baby and adult heights. A large variability was observed between morning and afternoon runs (Fig. 2) during two scenarios (Figs. 3 and 4) with maximum variability noted for PNCs

(62% for $\text{SP}_{\text{FR-WC}}$), followed by $\text{PM}_{2.5-10}$ (57% for $\text{SP}_{\text{FP-WC}}$) and nearly identical for PM_1 (8% for $\text{SP}_{\text{FP-WC}}$) and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ (7% for $\text{SP}_{\text{FR-WC}}$). The concentrations of the finer fraction (PM_1 , $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, and PNC) can be higher or lower depending on the traffic volume during morning/evening hours (SI Section S1). This trend was reflected by the fine fraction; for example, the concentrations of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ were higher during the morning due to relatively higher traffic volume during morning peak compared with afternoon hours. The coarse fraction is driven by re-suspension effects. In line with previous work (Kumar et al., 2017), we

Fig. 3. Bar charts comparing pram versus adult height concentration exposures for (a) PM₁ (μg m⁻³);(b)PM_{2.5} (μg m⁻³);(c) PM_{2.5-10} (μg m⁻³); (d) PM₁₀ (μg m⁻³); and (e) PNC (#cm⁻³) in single pram during morning and afternoon. Note that. The concentrations shown on y-axis are overall average obtained after averaging all runs for specified scenarios (SP_{FP-WC}; SP_{FR-WC}) at 1-minute interval. The field data is collected at 6 s resolution and then averaged to 1-minute interval. The error bars refer to standard deviation; BB and AD refer to pram height and adult heights, respectively. SP_{FP} refers to single pram facing parent while SP_{FR} refers to single pram facing roadside.

Fig. 4. In-pram baby versus adult exposure concentrations (scenario average) in single and double pram for (a) morning PNC concentration; and (b) afternoon time PNC concentration. Note that the different scenarios refers to typical microenvironment of in-pram field measurements (such as, type of pram used, use of pram cover) and briefly explained as follows: (1) SP_{FP-WC} – Single Pram (facing parent-without cover); (2) SP_{FP-C} – Single Pram (facing parent-with cover); (3) SP_{FR-WC} – Single Pram (facing roadside - without cover); (4) SP_{FR-C} – Single Pram (facing roadside -with cover); (5) DP_{FR-WC} – Double Pram (facing roadside - without cover). Please note the concentrations shown on y-axis are overall average obtained after averaging all runs for specified scenarios (SP_{FP-WC}; SP_{FR-WC}) at 1-minute interval. The field data is collected at 6 s resolution and then averaged to 1-minute interval.

measured relatively higher concentrations (SP_{FR-WC}, $9 \pm 3.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) of PM_{2.5-10} during afternoon compared with morning (SP_{FR-WC}, $6 \pm 3.4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). The average RH was $\sim 38\%$ higher during the morning than in the afternoon (SI Table S4). These meteorological differences are plotted for comparison purposes as shown in SI Fig. S4. The overnight dew and resulting wetness to road surface may have suppressed the resuspension of coarse particles during morning hours regardless of similar traffic volume during both times (Kumar et al., 2017; Sharma and Kumar, 2018).

As for the differences between in-pram and adult heights, exposure concentrations of PM_{2.5} (Fig. 3) and PNCs during morning hours under SP_{FR-WC} scenario (Fig. 4) were up to 31% higher at in-pram height compared to adult height (p-value < 0.001). During the afternoon, the corresponding differences in PM_{2.5} increased to about 44% at in-pram height ($16 \pm 7 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) compared to adult height ($9 \pm 3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$; Fig. 3, p-value < 0.001). In-pram PNCs during afternoon were about 27% lower than those at adult breathing height ($5854 \pm 3041 \text{ cm}^{-3}$; p-value < 0.001; Fig. 4). For coarse particles, exposure concentrations during the morning were 50% lower at in-pram height ($6 \pm 3.4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) compared to adult height ($12 \pm 9.8 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) with an opposite trend during afternoon hours (22% higher at in-pram height, $9 \pm 3.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ compared to adult height, $7 \pm 1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$).

Overnight dew conditions, traffic volume, and meteorological conditions could explain the observed variability (SI Tables S4). For example, Grundström et al. (2015) studied trends in coarse particles in the urban open-road environment (Gothenburg City Centre, Sweden) for wind speed < 2 m s^{-1} and > 5 m s^{-1} . They found that for wind speed < 2 m s^{-1} concentrations of coarse particles decreased non-linearly with increasing wind speed, while a reverse (mildly positive) trend was found for wind speeds > 5 m s^{-1} . Basically, wind speed influences the dispersion of PM from the sources at street-level (Jones et al., 2010) and the concentrations of coarse particles can increase at low wind speed due to limited dilution and stronger resuspension at

high wind speeds (Grundström et al., 2015). Likewise, the mixing of street-level air with much cleaner above the street-level (i.e., urban background air) can also decrease average PNCs at higher wind speed (Janhall and Hallquist, 2005; Kumar et al., 2008a; Kumar et al., 2008b). However, greater wind speed can have a contrasting effect on some of its sources (re-suspension of road dust) for PM₁₀ (Grundström et al., 2015). As shown by the correlation matrix in SI Fig. S4, PNC showed poor correlation with other ambient PM concentrations, while a negative correlation with wind speed and ambient temperature. Thus the meteorological conditions could disproportionately affect different types of pollutants to bring variability in observed exposure concentrations.

Further, we plotted the time series plots of exposure concentrations of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ (Fig. 5a and b) and PNC (Fig. 5c and d) for both morning and afternoon hours. These figures indicate that in-pram baby exposure is consistently higher than those at adult breathing height and the differences are distinct at pollution hotspots such as bus stops and traffic intersections. Our results are also in line with those reported for PNCs by Burtcher and Schüepf (2012). They found that pram height concentrations in the trailer were approximately 35% higher than at adult breathing height.

The ratio ($C_{\text{BH}}/C_{\text{AH}}$) indicates relative average concentrations of baby versus adult height with the mean value indicated by a horizontal line (Fig. 6). The average of $C_{\text{BH}}/C_{\text{AH}}$ values are consistently greater than 1 in all cases for both the PM and PNC, re-confirming greater exposure concentrations at baby height relative to adult height.

3.2. Peak concentration exposures at baby versus adult height

Fig. 7 shows the spatio-temporal variability of pollutant concentrations at pram and adult height, indicating that the concentrations are generally higher at pollution hotspots such as bus stops and TIs compared to the rest of the route. These are in line with those reported by Kumar et al. (2017), who observed relatively higher concentrations of fine particles (morning, 7%; afternoon 10%) and coarse particles (morning, 19%; afternoon 10%) at TIs compared to the rest of the route. We also observe that there are sections of the route other than pollution hotspots where concentrations are almost comparable to the pollution hotspots. These are likely due to the accumulation of pollutants due to the hindered dispersion of pollutants due to the street canyon effect of surrounding buildings on busy roads in the town centre (Gallagher et al., 2015; Kumar et al., 2009).

To understand the differences in peak intensity exposure concentrations of baby versus adult heights for PM, we segregated raw data of PM (PM₁, PM_{2.5}, PM_{2.5-10} and PM₁₀) at 6 s resolution into three different quartiles – (i) < 25 percentile, (ii) > 25 < 75 percentile, and (iii) > 75 percentile – for morning and afternoon times. The concentrations of different pollutants are first organised scenario-wise and then they are separated into the above discussed three quartiles which are then averaged for respective quartiles. These three quartiles represent low, moderate and peak concentrations. Fig. 8 shows these quartile values for two selected scenarios: SP_{FP-WC} (Fig. 8a and b) and SP_{FR-WC} (Fig. 8c and d). We selected these scenarios explicitly since our goal from this analysis is to understand the variability in peak concentrations at baby versus adult heights. The analysis for scenario SP_{FP-WC} (Fig. 8a–c; SI Table S9) showed that in-pram height concentrations were higher compared with adult height in all three quartiles for (i) PM₁ (63%, 61%, 62%); (ii) PM_{2.5} (62%, 55%, 50%) and; (iii) PM_{2.5-10} (36%, 22%, 8%). A similar trend was observed for the SP_{FR-WC} scenario with higher concentrations at baby height relative to adult height as follows: (i) PM₁ (morning: 50%, 49%, 50%); (ii) PM_{2.5} (29%, 46%, 44%); (iii) and; PM_{2.5-10} (50%, 33%, 20%) (SI Table S9).

The trend of higher PM concentrations for in-pram height is consistent across all three quartiles for both the scenarios (SP_{FP-WC} and

Fig. 5. Time series of concentrations at pram and adult heights during (a) afternoon PM_{2.5} ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) and (b) afternoon PM₁₀ (run average; $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) for measurements on 16th August 2018 at pram height versus adult height; (c) morning PNC concentration ($\#\text{cm}^{-3}$); and (d) afternoon PNC concentration ($\#\text{cm}^{-3}$). The route is divided into 5 segments – (i) UC (University campus), (ii) BS_{AX} (on campus bus stop AX in front of AX building), (iii) TC (town centre), (iv) TI₁ (traffic intersection 1 in front of church) and; (v) TI₂ (Traffic intersection 2 in front of Waitrose near the destination i.e., Sandfield Primary School). There is a stopover of 15 min at first university campus bus stop (BS_{AX}) for stationary measurements while there was no stopover at second university bus stop (BS_{HS}) which refers to university campus Health Science bus stop.

SP_{FR-WC}). It can be seen from these results that concentrations of coarse particles (PM_{2.5-10} and PM₁₀) are generally higher during afternoon periods specifically for upper quartile ranges (25–75 percentile and > 75 percentile) compared to morning periods (SI Table S9), presumably for the reasons explained in Section 2.1.

3.3. Exposure concentrations in a double pram

Double prams have seats either in parallel or at different heights. Here, we assess the variabilities in exposure concentrations of PM and PNCs at two different measurement heights: top and the bottom seat of a double pram facing roadside (Fig. 9). In general, the differences between the two top and bottom seats were modest. For example, the average concentrations of overall runs for fine particles (PM_{2.5}) at the bottom seat ($14 \pm 7 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) were slightly higher than those at top seat concentration ($13 \pm 5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) during morning hours. During the afternoon, top seat ($11 \pm 5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) experienced slightly higher concentrations than at the bottom seat ($9 \pm 5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). A similar trend was seen for coarse particles with modest differences, i.e., bottom ($12 \pm 3.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) and top ($9 \pm 6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) seat concentrations during morning compared to those at the bottom ($8 \pm 2 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) and

top ($5 \pm 2 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) seats during the afternoon.

For PNCs in double prams (combining all DP_{FR-WC}; double pram facing roadside without cover; Fig. 9), the morning was significantly higher (70%) for the bottom seat ($14738 \pm 12199 \text{ cm}^{-3}$) compared to top seat ($4448 \pm 2066 \text{ cm}^{-3}$). During the afternoon, this difference was almost similar (72%) to $5059 \pm 2448 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (bottom seat) compared with $1431 \pm 523 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (top seat). Generally, the PNCs and fine particles at the bottom seat of double pram exceeded those at the top seat, absolute differences were not appreciably different to present a clear trend.

There are no past studies for direct comparison with our results. Hence, we compare our results with studies focussed around vertical concentration profiles of particles (Goel and Kumar, 2016; Kumar et al., 2008a; Kumar et al., 2008b; Li et al., 2007; Weber et al., 2006). Usually, a decreasing concentration trend of PM_{2.5} and PNC with height can be expected in roadside environments (Goel and Kumar, 2016; Li et al., 2007). However, it is also noted that the region within the first two meters near the road is exceptionally turbulent as a result of enhanced traffic produced turbulence near the ground from vehicle movements (Di Sabatino et al., 2003). Therefore varying trends can be expected depending on the traffic volume count, proximity with the vehicle

Fig. 6. Timeseries scatter plots of relative concentrations (C_{BH}/C_{AH}) at baby versus adult height for (a) PM_1 (morning), (b) PM_1 (afternoon), (c) $PM_{2.5}$ (morning), (d) $PM_{2.5}$ (afternoon), (e) PM_{10} and; (f) PM_{10} (afternoon), (g) PNC (morning); and (h) PNC (afternoon). Please note that C_{BH}/C_{AH} is the ratio of exposures at baby to adult heights. Colours represent the relative density of data points, with blue indicating low density and red indicating high density. The fitted constant values are marked with black lines.

tailpipe, and environmental conditions on a particular route (Kumar et al., 2008a).

3.4. Efficacy of pram covers

We compared the two scenarios – single pram facing roadside without cover (SP_{FR-WC}) and with cover (SP_{FR-C}) – to evaluate the efficiency of pram covers in mitigating in-pram babies' exposure to selected PM and PNC. Fig. 4 shows the scenario averaged concentrations of PNC ($\#cm^{-3}$) during morning and afternoon hours. Although the differences in absolute concentrations were minimal, the comparison of average fine and coarse particle concentrations ($\mu g m^{-3}$) for the two scenarios showed that the use of pram cover led to about 39% and 36% concentration reduction to fine particle concentrations during morning and afternoon, respectively. Interestingly, a mixed trend is observed for coarse particles, showing an almost negligible difference in concentrations during morning hours while reduction of almost 43% in

concentrations during afternoon hours because of using a pram cover. A mixed trend was observed for PNC, showing by up to 23% increase in PNC while using cover compared with the no-cover case during morning hours and up to about 5% reduction during afternoon hours (Fig. 4). Typically the presence of physical barriers, such as noise and vegetation, have shown to show a decline in pollutant concentrations on their downwind side (Abhijith and Kumar, 2019; Baldauf, 2017; Schulte et al., 2014; Ottosen and Kumar, 2020). Likewise, pram covers when utilised for shorter periods to avoid an accumulation of exhaled carbon dioxide in cold weather conditions at pollution hotspots (e.g., traffic intersections and bus stands) should act as physical barriers between the exhaust emissions from road vehicles and breathing area to help reduce their exposure (Sharma and Kumar, 2018). However, when used in hot weather conditions, they could possibly trap the heat underneath them, restrict air circulation and could generate suffocating conditions inside the in-pram breathing zone (Koch, 2008; Sharma and Kumar, 2018). The pram covers used in our experiments were of

Fig. 7. Spatial variability of PM₁₀ concentration profiles at (a) pram, and (b) adult heights. The PM₁₀ concentration range was split into 5 colour categories by referring to the corresponding legend.

Fig. 8. Bar plots showing PM₁, PM_{2.5}, PM_{2.5-10} and PM₁₀ concentration intensities at baby versus adult heights in three quartile ranges, < 25 percentile, 25–75 and > 75 during (a) morning SP_{FP-WC} scenario (single pram facing parent without cover); (b) afternoon SP_{FP-WC} scenario; (c) morning SP_{FR-WC} scenario (single pram facing road without cover); and (d) afternoon SP_{FR-WC} scenario.

Fig. 9. Bar charts comparing average PM concentration ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) at double pram top seat height versus bottom seat height for morning and afternoon time measurements.

standard configuration which comes as relatively porous. These openings may have permitted the inflow of outside pollutants. SI Figure S6 shows the details of pram cover fitted on the single and double pram facing roadside.

As explained above, the reduction in fine particles and PNC concentrations could possibly be understood by the barrier effect provided by the pram cover to limit the fresh exhaust emissions. However, an opposite trend for coarse particles with relatively increased concentrations under pram cover was unclear. In a different context, Kumar and Goel (2016) found a strong positive exponential correlation for fine particles with the air exchange rates under different ventilation settings of in-car cabin measurements and an opposite trend was seen for coarse particles. In our context, the restricted ventilation with cover may have led to the accumulation of coarse particles but further investigations are warranted to understand the key underlining reasons.

3.5. Physico-chemical analysis

The SEM images showed the very fine details of blank filter composition and the size and shape of the dominant elements on collected PM mass on the exposed filters (Fig. 10). We captured the SEM images at 10 kV and three magnifications including 1000, 2000 and 3000, so that essential finer details (such as particle morphology, etc) of collected particles on the filter samples could be captured and also facilitate comparison of results with similar past study (Kumar et al., 2017). A diverse structure of the sampled particles was found consisting of irregular shaped, aggregated and spongy particles. A few asymmetrical black holes can also be seen, which represent the porosity of the filters (Fig. 10).

The EDS analysis of blank filter showed the filter composition to be dominated by Florine (F) as 88.8 wt% and Carbon (C) as 11.2 wt% (SI Table S10). The morphologies of the particles showed the presence of

elements from multiple sources such as the earth crust materials, the vehicle exhaust and traffic-induced re-suspension of road dust and tyre and brake wear (magnetite, Fe_3O_4 from erosion of cast-iron disc brakes) emissions (Amato et al., 2016; Kumar et al., 2013; Sharma and Kumar, 2018). The review of existing literature suggest that a major proportion (~70%) of the brake wear is usually contributed by the discs and only 30% from the brake pads (Hulskotte et al., 2014) with average brake discs profile showing predominance of Fe (brake discs, 95%; brake pad, 20%), Cu as friction material (brake discs, < 1%; brake pad, 10%) and traces of other metals such as Al, Ca, Zn and Sn (Amato et al., 2016; Hulskotte et al., 2014). The particles collected at baby height showed higher percentages of Fe (51% higher) and Cu (47%) compared to adult height (Fig. S5), presumably because sampling at baby height is closer to the vehicle tailpipe with Fe being a tracer of non-exhaust emissions from brake- and tyre-wear (Amato et al., 2016) while S is likely contributed from tyre-wear emissions (Amato et al., 2011). Apart from these elements, road salt in the form of crystal sodium chloride (NaCl) is believed to make a reasonable contribution towards the PM. The elements Na and Cl, comprising road salt were scarcely found at the pram height and adult height samples as opposed to their relatively greater contribution reported by Kumar et al. (2017). This is likely due to the presence of road salt from the de-icing of roads during their measurements (UK winter periods, January to February) as opposed to this study from August to September. A relatively higher contribution from crustal species (e.g., Ca, Al, Mg) was found at adult height filter samples as these are commonly found species in urban dust profiles (Amato et al., 2011). Overall, the SEM and EDS analysis revealed that there is an appreciable contribution from non-exhaust emissions such as re-suspended road dust, brake wear and tire wear emissions with the predominance of brake and tyre-wear emissions at baby height compared to a relatively larger share of earth crust elements at adult height.

Fig. 10. SEM images of (a) PTFE blank filter samples; (b) mass collected at baby height; (c) mass collected at adult height; (d–e) mass collected at adult height stationary measurements.

4. Summary, conclusions and future work

The exposure to fine and ultrafine particles at in-pram, adult and different seating heights were assessed. The passive mitigation options in the form of understanding the effect of pram covers on reduced exposure were examined.

The review of existing literature focussed on negative health effects of TRAP exposure to young children highlighted that:

- Young children have rapidly growing and developing organ systems

and TRAP can affect their neurodevelopment, respiratory systems, cognitive development, and lower functional integration and segregation in key brain networks, including slower brain maturation. These impacts become more important for young children due to their higher breathing rates in proportion to their lung size and body weight compared with adults.

The assessment of the variabilities in measured concentrations of pollutants (PM and PNC) during morning versus afternoon hours of the day allowed to conclude that:

- Large variability was observed between the runs performed during different times of the day (morning versus afternoon), and scenarios with maximum variability noted up to 62% for PNCs between morning and afternoon hours.

The analysis of trends in temporal variations of PM and PNC exposure concentrations at in-pram versus adult breathing heights showed that:

- The overall averaged concentration exposure at in-pram breathing height was generally higher compared to adult breathing height for fine particles and PNC.
- The concentrations were found to be relatively higher at pollution hotspots such as bus stops and TIs compared to the rest of the route. We also observed the effects of surrounding buildings on some part of the route where despite free-flow traffic the concentrations were comparable to those observed at bus stops or TIs.

The analysis of differences in peak intensity exposure concentrations of baby versus adult heights for pollutants (PM and PNC) revealed that:

- Peak concentration differences for in-pram versus adult height are generally higher for fine particles compared to coarse particles.

The comparative analysis of exposure concentrations of PM and PNCs at two different measurement heights (top and bottom seats) of a double pram facing roadside showed that:

- Usually, the concentrations at the bottom seat were relatively larger but the differences were not significant to able to establish a clear trend.

The evaluation of the efficiency of pram covers in mitigating in-pram babies' exposure to selected PM and PNC (scenarios, SP_{FR-WC} and SP_{FR-C}) showed that:

- Pram covers are effective in reducing concentrations of fine and coarse particles but showed mixed trends for PNC concentrations, highlighting the need for further investigations to establish the underlining reasons.

The experimental analysis of the physico-chemical properties of particles inhaled at in-pram height via SEM showed that:

- An extensive spread of morphologies and agglomerates emitted from vehicle exhaust as well as earth crust minerals were seen. The EDS analysis pointed out the predominance of the brake- and tyre-wear emissions at baby height compared to a relatively larger share of earth crust elements at adult height.

In the polluted roadside environments, concentrations of the fine (PM_{10} , $PM_{2.5}$) and ultrafine (PNC) fractions could show varying trends with height within first two meters depending on the traffic volume count, proximity with the vehicle tailpipe, and environmental conditions (i.e., wind speed and wind direction) on a particular route (Kumar et al., 2008a). In contrast, the coarse fraction is significantly affected by resuspension effects. On any given route, there could be segments on the route where concentrations may reach levels close to the pollution hotspots (e.g., bus stops, TIs). These might result from the accumulation of pollutants due to restricted dispersion owing to the street canyon effect of surrounding buildings on busy roads in the town centre (Kumar et al., 2009).

This study covered in-pram exposures and their comparison with adult height exposures and provides critical analysis for both single and double pram types with varying breathing heights. The study also

provides meaningful insights as an attempt to build a knowledge base to extend the understanding of the differences in in-pram exposure concentrations while also introduces findings of the efficacy of pram covers as a potential mitigation option. Pram covers with standard openings could be utilised for shorter periods in cold weather conditions at pollution hotspots (e.g., traffic intersections and bus stands) to act as physical barriers between vehicle exhaust emissions and in-pram breathing area. However, their use is not recommended for extended periods in hot weather conditions.

The study highlighted a need for further investigations surrounding the efficacy of pram covers focusing on different size fractions, especially coarse particles, besides establishing exposure profiles for different types of prams under diverse meteorological and built environment conditions to allow establishing a broad database.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ashish Sharma: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing - original draft. **Prashant Kumar:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Writing - review & editing.

Acknowledgements

This work has been carried out under the framework of the MAPE Project (Mitigation of air pollution exposure to young children; EPSRC Project reference number 1948919). The authors acknowledge the funding support from the University of Surrey, EPSRC PhD studentship and industrial collaboration with BRIZI Ltd. The authors thank Professor John F Watts for his support and several GCARE researchers for volunteering in fieldwork. The views presented in this paper are of authors, except otherwise indicated. The authors do not certify, endorse or recommend any trade names or commercial products referred to this article.

Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.105671>.

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